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THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF UZBEK SCHOLAR SATTOROV T.K TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Hayitaliyeva Farzona

Student, English Philology Faculty

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

E-mail: farzonahon004@icloud.com

Scientific advisor: **Klara Nazmutdinova**

ESL teacher of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

E-mail: klaranazmutdinova@gmail.com

***Abstract.** Sattarov Tojimat's contributions are part of Uzbekistan's broader strategy of international cooperation with institutions such as the British Council and the Confucius Institute, which promote language skills as a tool for academic and professional advancement.*

Key words. Achievements of Tojimat Sattarov in education, work and in the life, best contributor of Uzbekistan, books, teaching

Introduction Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Tojimat Sattarov Kodirovich was born in Fergana, on 12th of April in a working family. First, he studied for eight years in a school located in his village. From the time he was at school, he tried to publish articles in district, regional, and republican newspapers. After his school graduation in 1965, he applied and became a student in foreign language faculty in a university in Khojand, Fergana. He did his best to study by heart, and learned Russian and other languages at the same time. He also asked help from his teachers at university to succeed in education as he was so willing to learn more and more new things. He graduated university in 1969 and started working as an English teacher at that university and became one of the most favorite teachers of his students like his own teachers while his study. First of all, Tojimat Sattarov paid more attention to searching, academic works, and during 1970-1975, he wrote reviews for English language books for schoolchildren, and they were also published in popular newspapers.

Main part Tojimat Sattarov wrote a lot of academic works and books, one of them is called “English for Law Students” which is important to learn for students studying law. This book includes 16 units which are all about legal topics, and also contains linguistic material, conversational phrases, texts for skimming and scanning, topic-based vocabularies and exercises. This book is designed for students to learn and improve listening, reading, writing, and speaking skills. He thought that, English is very important for legal profession, and law teacher and students should know English and be able to understand, speak and write in it, as this language helps them in their study, working fields, promotion and recreation, too. As it was mentioned above, there are 16 special topics in this book that they tell us about law, from general introductory topics (about himself, his institute, the Republic of Uzbekistan) to the Constitution, legal, judicial and executive bodies of Uzbekistan, the UK, and the USA. He designed his book as it is taught in the

second year of study. The comparison studies between the UK and the USA students, their legislative, executive and judicial bodies that motivate learners to speak fluently and read have been paid more attention. There is a field of Linguistic material which also contains vocabulary section, word-building, grammar section. And another one is conversational phrases and texts. Separate books on Reference Grammar, Home-reading supports this book, too. Tojimat Sattorov has really important role in foreign language learning and teaching in Uzbekistan through his various contributions. His work enhances language education quality by modern approaches, such as Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), which includes four English skills, listening, reading, speaking and writing. These are so beneficial to be able to be like a native and can totally understand, speak, write, listen comprehensibly and read everything. With this test students can have a certificate and apply for universities in Uzbekistan, or teach students, but unfortunately, this certificate helps students across only Uzbekistan. In his books, Tojimat Sattorov wrote rules of English grammar structures and explained how to use them in an easy and useful way. For example, one of his books includes articles, adverb, adjective (its degrees), all tenses, Suffix and prefixes and other more and more topics. He forms all topics including firstly, the topic name, linguistic materials, conversational phrases, texts, and different exercises and advices that are about how to pronounce the words correctly, how to make easy and complex sentences with different tenses, passive voice, linking words which is really crucial and useful to learn and use them.

Conclusion According to Tojimat Sattorov's point of view about learning and teaching foreign languages, greetings are also important between Uzbeks and Americans. A descriptive and cross-cultural analysis of verbal and non-verbal greetings used between Uzbeks and Americans is presented. Aspects covered include: general greeting usage patterns; their frequency and distribution in particular social situations in relation to the speakers; profession, age, gender and social position; social factors influencing health choices; social models of greetings; and the commonalities and differences in greetings between university

students and teachers of Uzbek and American cultures. Situations observed included student and faculty encounters at work around the university, in hallways and classrooms, on the street, at ceremonies and informal social gatherings, and in dormitories.

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VIRTUAL REALITY AND AUGMENTED REALITY FOR IMMERSIVE LANGUAGE LEARNING

Hayitmurodova Gulnur Zafarovna

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

English philology faculty

gulinurhayitmurodova162@gmail.com

***Abstract.** This article sheds light on the potential of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) to create interactive and engaging language learning environments. It also gives general information about these technologies, their profound contribution to teaching and learning foreign languages and how to use them effectively in educational settings.*

***Keywords.** Languages, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Technologies, Teaching, Education, Learning Environments*